

Co-creating AI experimentation ecosystems: Designing business and governance models for Smart Cities

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Abstract

As the European Union advances its AI regulatory agenda, cities are becoming critical arenas for testing and validating emerging technologies under real-life conditions. This paper examines how AI Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs), a hybrid form between testbeds, sandboxes and Living Labs, can be organized as distributed, node-based ecosystems to support responsible innovation in urban environments. Drawing on insights from the Digital Europe project CitCom.AI, spanning over a dozen TEF nodes across Europe, we explore how cities and regional actors can implement shared experimentation infrastructures while retaining local autonomy and regulatory alignment. The paper builds on a dual theoretical framework combining Multi-Level Governance and Business Ecosystem Theory. Through mixed methods, we investigate how governance structures, business models, and service specializations are evolving across the network. Preliminary findings suggest a set of core design principles for TEFs; role complementarity over service replication, distributed governance with aligned ethical standards, service interoperability across nodes, stakeholder-anchored validation, and regulatory readiness as a built-in service. These principles offer a blueprint for structuring TEFs that are adaptable to different urban contexts yet coordinated through a shared European vision. Our contribution supports the development of scalable, trusted, and citizen-centred AI innovation frameworks across smart cities in Europe. We also contribute to the literature on sustainable business models for Living Labs and to the literature on Living Labs for emerging technologies.

Key words

Smart cities, multi-level governance, business ecosystems, testing and experimentation facilities (TEFs), business models, sustainability, Living Labs for emerging technologies.

Introduction

The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) is compelling European cities, policymakers, and technology providers to reassess how emerging technologies are tested, governed, and scaled within urban environments. As the European Union strengthens its commitment to ethical, human-centric AI, reflected in initiatives such as the AI Act and the Digital Europe Programme, it must confront the dual challenge of encouraging trustworthy innovation while implementing effective regulatory oversight (Truby et al., 2022); (European Commission, 2024).

Traditionally, AI experimentation has been supported by three complementary models: testbeds, Living Labs, and regulatory sandboxes. Testbeds offer controlled environments for validating technologies in a structured, technical context (Sherwood et al., 2010); (Zapriala et al., 1995). Living Labs emphasize participatory innovation and stakeholder engagement in real-world settings (Leminen et al., 2012); (Schuurman, 2015). Regulatory sandboxes provide temporary, supervised environments where innovations can be tested under adapted legal frameworks (Buocz et al., 2023); (Yordanova, 2019).

Building on these foundations, this paper explores the business and governance dimensions of developing AI Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs) for smart cities; large-scale, real-world environments that support the deployment, validation, and responsible oversight of AI technologies. These facilities reflect the European Commission's vision for robust ecosystems that bring together technological capability, regulatory adaptability, and societal engagement. In the context of smart cities, TEFs benefit from Living Lab principles, enabling collaborative experimentation that is locally anchored yet aligned with broader European values.

Drawing on empirical insights from over a dozen CitCom.AI TEF initiatives across Europe, we investigate how these facilities can be organized as ecosystems of interlinked nodes⁷; each offering specialized business, regulatory, or technical services. Our focus is not on a single initiative, but on the development of a generalizable business and governance model that can coordinate such distributed environments effectively. This includes mechanisms for value creation, stakeholder alignment, funding structures, and operational sustainability.

⁷ The CitCom.AI TEF consists of 10 nodes located in countries across Europe, each providing one or more services to support the testing and experimentation of AI solutions in real-life conditions.

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We argue that structuring AI experimentation as a networked ecosystem offers a scalable, resilient model for innovation in smart cities. This approach allows for regulatory diversity, respects local autonomy, and ensures that public value and ethical oversight are integral to how AI technologies are developed and deployed across Europe. This research also contributes to the literature on Living Labs business models and Living Labs for emerging technologies.

Theoretical framework

This paper draws on the theory of Multi-Level Governance (MLG) to frame the organizational and institutional dynamics involved in developing AI TEFs across European smart cities and communities. MLG, as developed in European governance literature, refers to the dispersion of authority across multiple, interacting levels of government, namely local, national, and supranational, rather than being concentrated in a single centre (Marks & Hooghe, 2004). This framework is particularly relevant in the context of the European Union's AI regulation, where cities must align with overarching EU values and legal instruments while retaining the autonomy to design and implement locally appropriate innovation strategies.

Recent research has demonstrated the relevance of MLG to smart cities in Europe. Van der Heijden (2017), for instance, highlights how EU institutions, national governments, and municipalities interact to shape smart city initiatives, creating both opportunities and coordination challenges in policy implementation and innovation delivery.

In this context, TEFs operate not as isolated pilots but as nodes within a coordinated ecosystem of experimentation, where legal, technical, and ethical considerations intersect. To maximize value and customer satisfaction, collaboration between AI innovators, cities, and communities is crucial, along with community building to encourage data sharing and trust (Schuurman et al., 2024a). MLG helps explain how regulatory responsibilities and innovation authority can be distributed across cities and EU institutions, enabling context-sensitive AI deployment under a shared regulatory umbrella.

To complement this institutional perspective, we also draw on Business Ecosystem Theory to understand how value is created and sustained across these distributed nodes. Inspired by Moore's (1993) original framing, this theory conceptualizes ecosystems as networks of interdependent actors (firms, institutions, and users) that co-evolve capabilities around a shared platform or innovation objective. In our case, the shared objective is the responsible deployment of AI in urban environments, facilitated by governance mechanisms that balance local initiative with European-wide coherence. Ecosystem engagement is crucial for testing facilities, because TEFs should aim to balance technical feasibility with real-world needs (Schuurman et al., 2024b).

Komninos and Mora (2018) apply this perspective directly to the European smart city context, showing how diverse public and private actors collaborate within dynamic

ecosystems to develop and scale digital solutions. Their findings underscore the importance of strategic coordination and role differentiation in sustaining innovation over time.

Figure 1. TEFs in European smart cities under dual lens

Together, MLG and Business Ecosystem Theory provide a dual lens: the former clarifies how regulatory and political coordination is managed across governance levels, while the latter offers insight into how diverse nodes in the TEF network generate complementary value and sustain operational viability.

Method

This paper adopts a mixed-method approach to explore the organizational and strategic design of AI Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs) within the CitCom.AI project. The research combines co-creation workshops, structured tools, and a follow-up survey to elicit insights from project partners across Europe. Our focus was on both the business logic and governance architecture of a multi-nodal smart city experimentation ecosystem.

Two co-creation workshops were conducted. The first focused on the business dimension of the TEF ecosystem. Twelve participants, comprising representatives from all CitCom.AI nodes, including city representatives, researchers, technology developers, and members of industry associations, they collaboratively completed an adapted version of the Business Model Canvas, they collaboratively completed an adapted version of the Business Model Canvas. The exercise was carried out in small groups or individually, using pre-defined scenarios to explore service offerings, key stakeholders, value propositions, and revenue or funding mechanisms.

The second workshop addressed the ecosystem and governance aspects of the TEF. Thirty-two participants that represented the different CitCom.ai nodes were present, their backgrounds spanning across all parts of the quadruple helix. Through a facilitated co-creation format, participants mapped their roles and relationships within the broader node network and discussed governance challenges, coordination mechanisms, and unique strengths of their respective sites. To complement the workshop data, a follow-up survey was distributed to all nodes to capture additional reflections on service complementarities, regulatory interfaces, and operational constraints.

These empirical cases represent over a dozen TEF nodes across Europe. The included nodes differ in institutional anchoring, with some led by municipalities, others by research institutions, and others by public–private consortia. This diversity provided rich comparative insights into how governance and business models can be shaped under varying local conditions. Data analysis combined thematic coding of qualitative inputs with descriptive statistics from survey responses.

This iterative, participatory process enabled us to derive preliminary design principles grounded in real-world experimentation environments, aligned with the co-creation and real-world innovation practices central to Living Labs.

Preliminary Results

Our initial findings, derived from cross-case analysis of experimentation sites within the CitCom.AI project, point to a set of emerging design principles for structuring AI TEFs as effective, scalable ecosystems. These principles reflect both the operational realities of multi-nodal environments, and the governance imperatives associated with responsible AI deployment in smart cities.

- **Complementarity over replication:** Effective TEFs benefit from nodes that specialize in distinct capabilities, such as technical validation, ethical oversight, or societal engagement, rather than duplicating services across sites. This specialization enhances the overall ecosystem’s efficiency and depth of expertise. This idea reinforces the Business Ecosystem Theory (Moore, 1993), since ecosystems thrive on role differentiation (Komninos & Mora, 2018; Moore, 1993).
- **Distributed governance with aligned standards:** Rather than enforcing central control, governance models should empower regional and city-level actors while maintaining coherence through shared ethical frameworks, compliance protocols, and procedural transparency. This proposition exemplifies MLG principles, where

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nodes retain autonomy yet follow shared ethical and compliance norms (Marks & Hooghe, 2004; Van der Heijden, 2017).

- **Service interoperability:** Nodes should function as part of a connected service infrastructure, enabling referral mechanisms that direct innovators to the most suitable expertise, whether legal, technical, or contextual.
- **Stakeholder-anchored validation:** Experimentation must involve local stakeholders; municipal authorities, SMEs, and citizen groups. This should happen from the outset to ensure social relevance, legitimacy, and early feedback loops. The importance of the involvement of the ecosystem was reflected in research by Schuurman et al. (2024b).
- **Regulatory readiness as a service:** TEFs should offer dedicated support services such as legal advisory, sandbox orchestration, and guidance toward pre-certification, helping innovators navigate complex regulatory landscapes early in the development cycle.

Figure 2. Design principles

These principles serve as a foundation for a scalable, business- and governance-oriented model of AI experimentation aligned with European values and suited to the urban diversity of smart cities.

Conclusions & future research

Within this paper, we presented the first findings of research into the long-term sustainability of CitCom.ai, one of the five Testing and Experimentation Facilities supported by the European Commission to foster innovative, but safe urban AI solutions. Currently, the dominant business model option seems to be a network of nodes where the complementarity of the geographically distributed testing sites is a key asset, and

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regulatory readiness could be a main driver for business success. However, there are still some issues to be resolved, such as an increased service, infrastructure and data interoperability, and a systematic involvement of the relevant stakeholders of the local ecosystem to enable early feedback loops. As next steps, information is collected on the different services provided and delivered at the different nodes, and on the customer profiles, interest and satisfaction. This will allow to iterate the current business model and sharpen the outlook of this 'network of nodes' approach. While our study draws on a limited number of early-stage cases, the diversity of participating nodes offers a strong comparative foundation. Scalability across different urban contexts remains challenging, especially in terms of harmonizing resources and aligning regulatory interpretations across EU member states. Yet these challenges also create opportunities: distributed networks such as CitCom.AI can serve as platforms for gradual standardization, cross-learning, and co-investment, thereby strengthening long-term sustainability. Future work should therefore focus not only on identifying barriers but also on leveraging the complementarities and adaptive capacities already visible within the TEF network. Moreover, it will be key to link this initiative with the blossoming, yet complex European data, AI and digital innovation ecosystem, as there seem to be quite some overlap between some of these (EU-funded)- initiatives. Therefore, we argue for more research into the long(er) term sustainability of these initiatives, and we believe that this 'network of nodes'-approach can also be used to link up with other, adjacent projects and initiatives.

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